

DESIGN, CONSTRUCTION AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF A MANUALLY OPERATED DOUGH KNEADING MACHINE FOR DOMESTIC USE

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ABSTRACT

Kneading is the process of working into dough by pummeling, massaging and stretching. The work presented here is the Design, Construction and Performance Evaluation of a manually operated Dough Kneading Machine for Domestic use and small scale bakeries to obtain a good quality pastry to replace the crude and cumbersome method of using rolling pins, bottles, tray and troughs. The Rollers, Worktable, Frame and Gears assembled together make up the Machine. The machine was constructed from locally sourced materials and tested. The result obtained gave a kneading efficiency of 78% with a kneading capacity of 33.3cm³/Sec.

INTRODUCTION

Dough can be defined as a mixture of flour and water with other ingredients, such as leavening agents, sugar, salt, egg and various flavoring materials used to make baked products. They are thick and elastic and can be shaped, kneaded and rolled.

In the processing of dough, kneading is an important stage whereby the mixture is worked by massaging, pummeling and stretching to produce homogenous dough which helps to expel excess gas and aid in the even development of yeast cells. It also helps to equalize temperature throughout the dough mass and cause the subdivision of gas bubbles formed to give uniformity and fineness to the grains (Kordylas, 1990). Domestically, this is presently done manually and repeatedly using Rolling Pins, Bottles and Tray. Which makes the process cumbersome and the desired texture cannot be achieved. Today's dough processing machines are very large and need about eight horse power to operate them as a result are expensive and bulky and the capacities far exceed that which is required for domestic use. Industrial revolution led to numerous invention and improvement in bread making and mechanized dough mixing machines. The steel roller mills were invented in Swaziland and are still in use today in the United States (Pylar, 1988).

The bread making machines were later invented in the US which performed the mixing, kneading, moulding, baking and packaging (Hui, 1992). It is a very large machine with sophisticated systems. Despite these advances, the need for a machine to cater for the domestic demand for baked products has still not been met.

It is intended here to design, construct and test a dough kneading machine which is simple and compact in size for domestic use with capacity of handling not more than 5kg of dough at a time. This will eliminate the tedious and primitive way of kneading dough using rolling pins (Cylindrical Wood), Bottle and Tray so as to enhance dough texture which could also be used in rural areas where there is no accessibility to electricity supply.

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

Brief Description of the Machine

The schematic diagram of the dough kneading machine is presented in Fig 1. It consists of a frame on which are mounted the rollers and the Worktable. The main drive shaft is integrated in the top roller and mounted on a ball bearing housed in the frame. A spur gear and a hand lever is keyed to the shaft at one end. The Spur gear enables the drive to be transmitted to the bottom roller to enable it rotate in opposing direction.

Table 1: Cost Estimate for the Manufacture of the Dough Kneading Machine

Item No	Description of materials/Operation	Parts Used for	Unit/Qty	Unit Price (₦)	Total Cost (₦)
1	M25mm Mild Steel Rod	Shaft	2	500:00	1000:00
2	30mmx30mm Mild Steel Angle Iron	Frame	Full Length	1000:00	1000:00
3	Ball Bearings	Bearing	4	150:00	600:00
4	Gears	Drive Mechanism	2	500:00	1000:00
5	Galvanized Steel Sheet (750mm x 400mm)	Work Table	1	1000.00	1000:00
6	Mild Steel Sheet (600mm x 600mm)	Bearing Cover	1	500:00	500:00
7	Mild Steel Welding Electrode (Gauge 12)	-	1 Pkt	1000:00	1000:00
8	M12 Nuts & Bolts	-	20	10:00	200:00
9	Local Transportation	-	-	600:00	600:00
10	Labour	-	-	2000:00	2000:00
11	Contingencies (10% of Total Cost)	-	-	960:00	910:00
	TOTAL COST				9,810:00

Table 2: Result of Performance and Time analysis after Test

S/No	Quantity of Dough	V_{uc}	ρ_{uc}	V_c	ρ_c	Time	Thickness
	(Kg)	(cm^3)	(Kg/m^3)	(cm^3)	(Kg/m^3)	(sec.)	(cm)
1	2.0	1670	1197	1333.3	1500	100	3.0
2	3.0	2505	1197	2000.0	1500	120	3.0
3	4.0	3340	1197	2666.6	1500	150	3.0
4	5.0	4175	1197	3333.3	1500	165	3.0

Mode of Operation

The machine operation is initiated by the operator winding the handle of the machine and the rotational motion is transmitted to the top roller via the shaft keyed to it. This motion is simultaneously transmitted to the bottom roller through the spur gear.

During this operation, the Dough is placed on the feeding platform and fed into the gap between the two rollers arranged vertically. The rollers pick the dough and compress it as it

is pulled between the roller gaps thus stretching and kneading the dough in the process. This is repeated until a desired texture of dough is obtained.

The initial parameter of the Design is the maximum theoretical effort that can be provided by an average person in the operation of the machine. The critical parts that required design are the Rollers, Shaft, Frame, Hand Lever and the selection of Gears and Bearings.

Figure 2: Graph of Volume of Dough (cm³) against Time (sec)

Component Design

Roller Design

The design of the rollers is analogous to the design of two parallel cylinders in contact under the action of a uniformly distributed stress between the two contacting surfaces. From Shigley and Mischike (2001), Eqn. 1, the maximum pressure between the rollers was determined to be 7.24 kN/m².

$$P_o = \frac{2P}{\pi bL} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where; P = radial load of roller, N
 L = length of contact surface, m
 b = width of rectangular contact surface, m

Shaft Design

For any solid shaft without axial loading the diameter of shaft from ASME CODE is given by Eqn. 2. For the shaft under consideration the diameter was found to be Φ22mm. (Khurmi and Gupta, 2003)

$$d^2 = \sqrt{\left[\frac{16}{\pi \sigma_s} \left(K_b M_b \right)^2 + \left(K_t M_t \right)^2 \right]} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where; d = Shaft Diameter, m
 K_b = Combined shock and fatigue factor of Bending Moment
 K_t = Combined shock and fatigue factor of Torsional Moment
 M_b = Bending Moment, Nm
 M_t = Torsional Moment, Nm
 σ_s = Allowable Combined shear stress for bending and torsional moment for mild steel (56MN/m²)

Key: 1 Hand lever, 2 Work Table, 3 Frame Stand, 4 Bearing, 5 Top Roller, 6 Spur Gear.

Figure 2: Schematic Diagram of the Dough Kneading machine

Key Design

A key is a piece of mild steel inserted in between the shaft and the hub of the hand lever in order to prevent relative motion between them. The design consideration is that of obtaining an appropriate key dimension for a given shaft diameter, for a $\Phi 22$ mm diameter mild steel shaft, a key dimension of 8mm x 7mm was obtained from Khurmi and Gupta (2003).

Work table Design

The work table provides a platform on which the rolled dough is fed and collected. It consists of two sections i.e. the feeding platform and the discharge platform. The design consideration is such as to withstand the handling load of the dough during kneading, and galvanized mild

steel was selected because it gives minimum coefficient of friction to the dough and does not easily corrode.

Frame Design

The Frame provides mounting points to all other components of the machine. Its design consideration is against critical load subjected to it. For the dough kneading machine, the slenderness ratio is less than 80 hence the column is short. Johnson relationship as presented by Khurmi and Gupta (2003) is appropriate for determining its critical load factor; this was obtained to be 800kg which far exceeds the working load of 45kg.

Gear Design

In the design of gears for specific duty operation, the maximum permissible working stress as given by the Levi's equation as presented by Khurmi and Gupta. (2003) in eqn 3

$$\sigma_w = \sigma_s + C_v \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where; σ_s = Allowable static stress ($56 \times 10^6 \text{N/m}^2$ for ordinary cast iron)
 C_v = Velocity factor depending upon the nature of gear cut and operating velocity (0.2).

Manufacturing Details

Mild steel materials were used in the overall manufacture of the machine except for the worktable where galvanized steel sheet was used because of the tendency of mild steel to react with dough ingredient. All the materials were sourced locally and from scrap yards within Yola metropolis. After determining the design specifications, the kneading machine frame was constructed with angle iron 30mm x 30mm as shown in Fig 2. Some members of the frame were welded while others were fastened with bolts and nuts. For the shafts a $\Phi 30\text{mm}$ diameter mild steel rod was procured and was cut to specified length using power hark saw and were later turned to 22mm diameter on the Lathe. A key way was also machined at one end to which the spur gears will be fitted. The rolled galvanized steel plates were welded by a web at both ends to the shafts. These were then placed in position as shown in Fig 2 after the bearings were fitted to them. The work table was made from galvanized steel sheet reinforced at the edges with mild steel angle iron welded to it.

Cost Estimate

Table 1 shows the cost estimate of the dough kneading machine to be ₦9, 810:00. The cost reflects the current market price in Jimeta-Yola. However, it is well known fact that unit price is several times more than the quantity based production (Dagwa and Ibhadode, 2005). The materials procured were based on the quantity needed for the manufacture of the machine. The cost of labour, local transportation and contingencies were also included in the costing.

Performance Test and Result

Performance test is usually carried out to determine functionality and performance characteristics of the machine. This is because establishing the performance characteristics of a system before putting it to use is important, (Mathew et al, 1990). This will give a better understanding of the machine and an edge in safeguarding it (Uhumnwangho et al, 2003). For the dough kneading machine, two tests were carried out on the machine; they include free rotation test and full load test, this is necessary in order to determine the performance characteristics of the machine. For the free rotation test, the machine was set to run without load to ensure that there are no abnormalities or noise vibration which may be as a result of improper alignment during construction.

To carry out the full load test, 2kg of dough was fed between the rollers and then rolled by rotating the hand lever such that the dough is picked and compressed. This was done repeatedly until satisfactory dough texture was achieved. The length of time over which the kneading operation took place was also recorded. The process was repeated with 3kg, 4kg and 5kg of dough and the performance test result was recorded as shown in Table 2.

Determination of Kneading Efficiency

The kneading efficiency was determined and found to be 78% from eqn 4 (Shigley and Mischike, 2001)

$$\eta_k = \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_{uc}} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where; ρ_c = Density of compressed dough kg/cm³
 ρ_{uc} = Density of uncompressed dough.kg/cm³

The kneading capacity was also obtained from eqn 5 to be 7kg/hr.

$$\frac{\text{Mass of Dough in Kg}}{\text{Time in sec}} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

From the result in Table 2, a graph of Volume (cm³) against Time (sec) was obtained as shown in Fig 2. From the graph, the kneading time increases with volume of dough quantity and presents a linear relationship with a slope of 33.3 this is to say 33.3cm³/Sec of dough could be kneaded in a unit time. The kneading capacity was found to be 7kg/hr with an efficiency of 78%.

CONCLUSION

The design and manufacture of the dough kneading machine was found to be successful at an estimated cost of ₦9, 810:00. The performance was satisfactory with a kneading efficiency of 78%. The result obtained showed a considerable increase in kneading time and reduced fatigue on the operator.

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Dahiru, D. Y *et al*; Continental J. Engineering Sciences 1: 20 - 26, 2007

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